

MODERN METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: usually before learning foreign languages, students have great interest in that language and motivation at the initial stage. They want to express their opinions in a foreign language, chat with peers in that language and learn about the people who speak that language, the country and the culture that will motivate kata to develop oral speech.

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The reforms carried out in our country on issues of improving the system of retraining and professional development of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions teaching foreign languages, including the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages", the decree "on measures to further improve the system of retraining , The decision"on measures for the further development of the higher education system " was an important step in bringing to a higher level the system of training of mature specialists who fully meet world standards for all areas of our republic.

Students need to learn new words consistently and adequately to develop their oral speech. Educators should develop useful activities so that students can learn and memorize new words. Classes should introduce the student to the word and context naturally and prepare him to be able to apply it. Theatrical performances, various games, creative writing and team Reading are good examples of this. Since the large number of students and limited class time cannot guarantee complete word learning, it is also necessary to introduce students to the types of classes they spend at home. Using resources such as dictionaries, sidebooks, word cards can be very effective. There are several activities for practicing the word that fall into two general categories:

1. Context-independent activity
2. Context-dependent activity.

Context-independent activity so far we have talked a lot about the benefits of teaching and practicing the word, but in some cases we have thought little that we can also use jobs other than avditori. The advantages and benefits of this type of activity are that tamoni saves time. Once a student has become familiar with the use of a word in a sentence to some extent, the use of a word, including outside, to remember its form and meaning can lead to U'ssig of oral speech. In these cases, students can be asked to check their vocabulary on the subject or write the words on the board to identify the words they do not remember so that the teacher can quickly identify them. Among the exercises that are useful for practicing the word, the following can be noted.

Mental attack-Mental attack exercises are very useful, the most important benefit of

which is the nature of activity, which brings to mind forgotten material. A word spoken by a single reader can be remembered by many readers.

Writing is one of the oldest and most popular class activities. Persian sources also give it as spelling. To make this activity as useful as possible, we must make changes to it. For example, a teacher may ask the student to interpret the word after reading and writing it. Also, the teacher reads the text at normal speed, and students in multi-person groups try to write it in full. The students themselves work on this.

Guess – choose the word you taught in a session and ask your language learners to guess. You can give them a little guidance before starting the game. The student who correctly guesses the word must choose the next word and ask his classmates to guess. Continue this game until there are 10-15 words in the lesson. Students should focus on the structure of the lexicon in this.

Proper structuring-activities in which an activity clearly engages the learner with morphology and grammar are another type of extra-contextual exercise. In specific word-related processes such as word construction and syntax, students can be better informed that they have mastered the language. Each requirement can build up to 1-7 sentences or phrases on average.

Bingo-place the pictures on the board, depending on the Class level. Primary classes may have up to 15. Select 5 images from your readers and write down their names in a notebook. Next, write the names of the pictures under them. If some language learners have written a word, you will give them a score if the spelling of the word is correct. The person who correctly writes the first word five words will receive a reward.

Context-dependent activity. Instead of more time-consuming activities, it is also possible to use Work That is specific to text processing. This is how you can familiarize your readers with their participation in the context. Some of these activities are as follows:

Listen. Listening to audiomatns in class teaches students how to use them in context, in addition to introducing them to new words. The advantage of reading poems, short texts, news and the like in the classroom is that the text reaches the ears of students without being cut and paused while reading.

A creative approach is another important way to practice in the classroom. In creative writing activities, students are more deeply involved with words than in any other activity and try to choose the right words. Writing short poems, epic texts and articles is an example of creative writing. It is also possible to encourage students to do this type of activity outside the classroom, in which case there are more opportunities for them to choose the right words. Think about ways to publish their developments somewhere to encourage them.

Translation. The use of translation has not been used in most teaching textbooks for a long time. However, considering one of the most important problems of language learners is the issue of translation, the importance of translation has been once again addressed. Using dictionaries and other resources, you can ask readers to translate a short text from their native language into the language under study and discuss the correctness of choosing equivalents.

Motivation determines the effectiveness of educational activities and the U'zalization of students. The quality and result of the activities of psychologists and educators meeting the requirements of the period depends primarily on the needs and desires, motivation of the individual, and it is motivation that leads to a specific goal-oriented activity, which leads to

the identification of methods for achieving the goal.

Usually before learning foreign languages, students have a great interest in that language and motivation at the initial stage. They want to express their opinions in a foreign language, chat with peers in that language and learn about the people who speak that language, the country and the culture that will motivate them to develop oral speech. But when the study of foreign language begins, difficulties arise in many students. Due to this and other factors, the interest of students decreases. Naturally, when interest decreases, the level of language acquisition, the quality of education falls. The role of motivation to overcome these problems is great.

Motivated students are usually students who actively participate in the lesson, express their interest in science and acquire knowledge well.

But we must not forget that in the motivation of students, the teacher occupies an important place. It is natural for a student to actively participate in the lesson if the teacher brings interesting information about the country and history of the language being studied, samples of literature in the same language in the course of the lesson, explains topics through modern pedagogical tools and interactive methods, enrich his lesson with audio and video files. In addition, motivation can also be seen in encouraging students, in applauding the group.

In the process of passing the text "grandfather's garden", I used interactive methods, interesting materials, graphic organizers. I also tried to applaud each of the students' responses, encourage them and create a creative-work environment in the course of the lesson. I tried to explain the incorrectly given answers not only directly saying that they were mistakes, but also through various examples and comments, feedback from the groupmates. As a result, each student in the group sought to be active in the course of the lesson, not to be ashamed to say their opinion and to apply with different questions on the topic. Eventually, students developed a freethinking skill.

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